

Understanding Preferences of University Students for Indoor Plant Attributes: A Thematic Exploration

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Abstract

This study explores the preferences of university students for indoor plant attributes, focusing on the ways in which plants are perceived, valued, and integrated into student lifestyles. Conducted at Horizon Campus, Sri Lanka, the research employed a qualitative exploratory approach with semi-structured, face-to-face interviews involving eighteen undergraduate students from diverse faculties. Data was analyzed manually through thematic analysis, allowing for the identification of recurring patterns and meanings. Findings revealed that students' preferences were shaped by a combination of practical, aesthetic, and psychological considerations. Compact size, ease of maintenance, and durability emerged as primary drivers of plant choice, with varieties such as snake plants, pothos, and succulents gaining favor due to their low care requirements. Beyond functionality, indoor plants were also recognized for their aesthetic appeal and their capacity to enhance concentration, reduce stress, and create positive living environments. However, challenges such as inconsistent care, inadequate sunlight, pest infestations, and limited knowledge constrained sustained ownership. Students also expressed enthusiasm for innovative solutions such as self-watering pots, reminder applications, and peer-based initiatives that could make plant care more accessible. The study highlights the dual role of indoor plants as both practical household additions and symbolic companions that support student well-being. By situating plant preferences within the context of youth culture, the research contributes to the growing body of work on sustainable lifestyles and environmental psychology in higher education.

Keywords: *Aesthetics; Indoor plants; Preferences; Psychological well-being; University students*